

MODAL TECHNIQUE FOR THREE-DIMENSIONAL STRESS ANALYSIS OF PLAIN WEAVE COMPOSITES

John Whitcomb
Kanthikannan Sreirangan
Clinton Chapman
Aerospace Engineering Department
Texas A&M University
College Station, Texas

ABSTRACT

Textile composites present a unique challenge to the stress analyst due to their large microstructure. A global/local method was developed which significantly reduces the computational challenge and retains reasonable accuracy. This method uses homogenized engineering properties for the global analysis. The nodal displacements from this global analysis are used to determine the magnitudes of a few fundamental modes. These magnitudes are used to scale and superpose refined local solutions for these fundamental modes. A stubby cantilevered plate subjected to end moment and transverse load was analyzed using the proposed method. The results were quite encouraging.

INTRODUCTION

Plain weave composites consist of interlaced fiber bundles which are impregnated with a resin and then cured. It is not practical to discretely model each fiber bundle even when analyzing a simple coupon. Instead, the analysis is divided into two stages: a global analysis and a local analysis. The global analysis uses some form of effective constitutive properties. This might take the form of homogenized engineering moduli or macro elements, which are finite elements which approximately account for the microstructure within a single element [1,2]. To obtain detailed stress information requires a subsequent local analysis which discretely models the individual fiber bundles and matrix pockets.

There are many global/local strategies [e.g. 3-6]. A critical step in all of these strategies is how to apply boundary conditions on the detailed local model based on nodal forces and displacements from a crude global model. In an earlier study, the displacements from the global model were imposed along the entire global/local boundary of the local model. [3] Compatibility is exactly satisfied by this procedure. However, this procedure resulted in excellent predictions of the stress distribution away from the global/local boundary, but large errors near the boundary. This paper describes a procedure which satisfies compatibility between the global and local models in an average sense. In particular, the magnitudes of a few basic deformation modes are determined from the global analysis and then imposed on the local model. The next section will describe the global/local method. Then the cantilevered plate configuration selected

for this evaluation and the finite element models will be described. Finally, a few results will be presented which illustrate the advantages of the technique.

DESCRIPTION OF GLOBAL/LOCAL METHOD

Fig. 1 shows a schematic of the global/local procedure. The global analysis was performed using effective engineering properties. The effective properties for interior cells were determined using periodic boundary conditions for an infinite array of unit cells. [7]. Because of free-surface effects [3], the effective properties are different for interior and exterior cells. For the exterior cells the properties E_x , E_y , ν_{yz} , and ν_{zx} were determined using a two unit cell model with free surfaces at the top and bottom (ie. $z = \pm 2c$, where $c = \text{mat thickness}$).

The nodal displacements from the global analysis were used to determine the magnitudes of the selected fundamental deformation modes for the region of interest. In this study the region of interest was simply a 1/8 subcell of a unit cell (referred to herein as simply a subcell) and was modeled by one of the 20-node elements in the global model. The displacements for the 20 nodes were used to determine the 20 coefficients in a tri-quadratic polynomial fit for each displacement component. These polynomial curve fits were differentiated to obtain the magnitudes of the particular modes. In particular, for this study 12 fundamental modes were selected which were assumed to be constant for a unit cell. There were 6 constant strain modes:

ϵ_x , ϵ_y , ϵ_z , ϵ_{xy} , ϵ_{yz} , and ϵ_{xz} . There were also 6 -flexure modes: $\epsilon_{x,y}$, $\epsilon_{x,z}$, $\epsilon_{y,z}$, $\epsilon_{y,x}$, $\epsilon_{z,x}$ and $\epsilon_{z,y}$. The comma in the subscript indicates differentiation. For example, the mode $\epsilon_{x,z}$ equals $\partial^2 u / \partial z \partial x$ evaluated at the centroid of the unit cell containing the subcell.

Because of symmetry and the invariance in the y-direction for the configuration studied, a maximum of only 5 were non-zero: ϵ_x , ϵ_z , ϵ_{xz} , $\epsilon_{x,z}$, and $\epsilon_{z,x}$. The refined local model was subjected to unit values of each mode. For an interior cell the modal magnitudes determined from the global analysis were then used to scale and superpose the interior unit modal solutions to obtain a refined solution for the selected region. For an exterior cell this procedure was modified, as described later in this section. This is essentially a higher order version of the traditional use of micromechanics in a structural analysis. It is not unusual to obtain a global solution using homogenized properties and then use the calculated global strains with the actual material properties or a unit cell analysis to determine local stresses. The difference is that traditionally the unit cell analysis is performed for constant strain modes only. The advantages of including the linear strain modes will be discussed in the Results and Discussion section.

It should also be noted that different boundary conditions were used to determine the interior and exterior unit modal solutions. The interior solutions were obtained from a model which assumed that the cell was buried inside an infinite array of cells. Only one exterior mode solution was used in this study: ϵ_x . The exterior ϵ_x mode solution was obtained using a model with two unit cells through the thickness (i.e. the z-direction) and an infinite number in the x- and y-directions. That is, there were traction-free surfaces at $z = \pm 2c$. The possibility of more free surfaces was not considered in this effort. Since the exterior ϵ_x mode also contains an ϵ_z component, it was necessary to account for this contribution when determining the magnitude of the pure ϵ_z mode to superpose. If one defines ν_{xz} to be the average Poisson's ratio for an exterior cell, then the modified ϵ_z mode is (ϵ_z from the global analysis) - ν_{xz} (ϵ_x from the global analysis).

CONFIGURATION

This section describes the cantilevered plate configuration and the finite element models selected for this initial evaluation of the global/local method. A simple three dimensional configuration was selected so that reference solutions could be obtained using conventional finite element modeling. Fig. 2 shows the configuration considered. The cantilevered length (x-direction) was 1.5 times the thickness. The plate was infinite in the y-direction. The nominal curvature in the y-direction was restrained to be zero by imposing zero normal displacements on the planes $y = \pm \lambda/2$. The fiber tows were assumed to follow a sinusoidal path. The ratio of the tow wavelength to the mat thickness was 1/3.

Two load cases were considered: constant moment and transverse end load. For both cases $v(x, \pm \lambda/2, z) = 0$. The other boundary conditions are as follows:

$$\text{Constant moment case: } u(0, y, z) = 0 \quad u(3\lambda, y, z) = .01 z \quad w(0, 0, 0) = 0$$

$$\text{Transverse end load: } u(0, y, z) = v(0, y, z) = w(0, y, z) = 0$$

Traction in the z-direction on the plane $x = 3\lambda$ was -16 MPa.

Figs. 1 and 2 show the meshes used for the reference solution and the global and local models for the global/local analysis. All of the models used 20-node solid elements. The global/local analysis uses far fewer elements and degrees of freedom. The difference would be even greater if more refined models were used.

The material properties used for the fiber tows and matrix pockets are shown in the following table.

	Tow		Matrix		Homogenized properties	
	modulus	strength*	modulus	strength*	modulus(I.C.)	modulus (E.C.)
E_{11}	206.50 GPa	1034/-689.5 MPa	3.45 GPa	103.4/-241.3 MPa	29.45 GPa	24.97 GPa
E_{22}	5.17 GPa	41.37/-117.2 MPa	3.45 GPa	103.4/-241.3 MPa	29.45 GPa	24.97 GPa
E_{33}	5.17 GPa	41.37/-117.2 MPa	3.45 GPa	103.4/-241.3 MPa	4.80 GPa	4.80 GPa
ν_{12}	0.25		0.35		0.09	0.16
ν_{13}	0.25		0.35		0.94	0.99
ν_{23}	0.25		0.35		0.94	0.99
G_{12}	2.39 GPa	68.95 MPa	1.28 GPa	89.6 MPa	1.96 GPa	1.96 GPa
G_{13}	2.39 GPa	68.95 MPa	1.28 GPa	89.6 MPa	2.64 GPa	2.64 GPa
G_{23}	2.39 GPa	68.95 MPa	1.28 GPa	89.6 MPa	2.64 GPa	2.64 GPa

I.C. = interior cell * Tension/compression strength
 E.C. = exterior cell

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stress distributions were determined for a cantilevered beam using a traditional finite element model using the proposed global/local procedure. Two subcells were examined in detail for each load case. One was in the interior and one was on the exterior of the plate. These subcells are shown shaded in Fig. 2. The stresses were normalized by the allowable for each stress component and the locations and magnitudes of the largest normalized stresses were identified. These normalized stresses can be considered failure indices for a maximum stress failure

criterion. The table below summarizes the results for several of the larger values.

Table 1. Summary of predicted critical locations.

	interior cell (G/L prediction)					exterior cell (G/L prediction)				
	location	σ_{ij}	F.I.	%e	%e ₁	location	σ_{ij}	F.I.	%e	%e ₁
Constant Moment	warp tow	σ_{13}	0.807	0	-100	warp tow	σ_{13}	2.628	-5	-25
	warp tow	σ_{33}	0.605	0	-100	warp tow	σ_{33}	1.927	-12	-31
	matrix	σ_{33}	0.573	0	-100	fill tow	σ_{23}	1.035	-32	-26
	fill tow	σ_{23}	0.365	0	-100	matrix	σ_{33}	1.000	-9	-10
	matrix	σ_{22}	0.273	0	-100	fill tow	σ_{11}	0.607	-17	-41
Transverse End Load	warp tow	σ_{13}	1.440	5	-7	warp tow	σ_{13}	2.786	22	-3
	warp tow	σ_{33}	1.097	4	-22	warp tow	σ_{33}	2.099	16	48
	matrix	σ_{13}	1.000	-2	-4	fill tow	σ_{23}	0.778	-37	-25
	matrix	σ_{33}	0.490	-1	-76	matrix	σ_{13}	0.574	13	7
	fill tow	σ_{13}	0.368	1	1	matrix	σ_{11}	0.548	-10	-41

σ_{ij} = actual stress component

F.I. = failure index = actual stress/allowable stress.

%e = error in the G/L prediction (linear modes included) w.r.t reference solution.

%e₁ = error in the G/L prediction (only constant modes) w.r.t reference solution.

In the table, the location is given as warp or fill tow or matrix pocket. Subsequent contour plots will give a more precise indication of the location of the largest failure indices. For both load conditions and subcell locations the normalized σ_{13} and σ_{33} were largest and the largest values were in the warp tows. The errors were zero for the interior subcell for the constant moment load case. This was expected. For the transverse load case the errors tended to be significantly smaller for the interior subcell than for the exterior one. The most critical failure indices were predicted very well for the interior subcell. Although the predictions were not as good for the exterior subcell, the predictions were generally much better than if only constant modes had been used.

Figs. 3 and 4 show normalized stress contours for the interior and exterior subcell warp tow for the transverse end load case. The most critical locations were in the warp tow and the critical stress components were σ_{33} and σ_{13} , so that is what is shown. The location and magnitude of the peak values are labeled. The figures show that the global/local procedure predicts the location of peak stress and the distribution quite well for the interior subcell and reasonably well for the exterior subcell.

SUMMARY

A global/local procedure was described for analyzing textile composites. The procedure would be equally applicable for other materials for which a characteristic unit cell can be identified. The initial evaluation of the method showed the technique is quite promising. It should be noted that in this study, a simple configuration was studied. Further evaluation is needed for more complex configurations. The major obstacle is obtaining reference solutions for complex

configurations. In fact, even for the current study only very coarse meshes were used for the reference and local solutions in order to limit the number of equations involved. For this reason, this paper did not discuss the significance of the stress components, but instead concentrated on showing that the proposed global/local technique predicts the same trends as a similarly refined traditional analysis. However, the global/local technique is far less costly than a traditional analysis.

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Figure 1 Modal superposition technique using strain modes.

Figure 2 Schematic of woven composite plate.

Figure 3 Comparison of predicted normalized stresses for warp tow in interior subcell for transverse end load case.

Figure 4 Comparison of predicted normalized stresses for warp tow in exterior subcell for transverse end load case.